

Evaluating hybrid seed production technology along with the new growth hormone Mangiferin

R. Singh and S. K. Sahoo, Department of Genetics and Plant Breeding, Institute of Agricultural Sciences, Banaras Hindu University, Varanasi 221005, India

Doubts have been raised about the economic viability of hybrid seed production as rice is predominantly a self-pollinated crop. An efficient seed production package is as important as improving cytotsterile lines and developing and evaluating hybrids. We attempted to evaluate hybrid seed production technology using the new growth hormone Mangiferin because the cost of gibberellic acid (GA_3) was high. Besides Mangiferin, glycine was also used to economize hybrid seed production in rice. Using GA_3 , boric acid, urea, Mangiferin, and glycine in different concentrations, we studied their effect on several characters in hybrids, such as duration of opening of florets, stigma exertion, angle of opened florets, plant height before and after spraying, panicle exertion at 5%, at 50% flowering, and at maturity, grain yield ha^{-1} , 1000-grain weight, and spikelet length. Analysis of variance showed highly significant differences for all the characters except panicle exertion at 50% flowering, which was significant only at 5%. In general, treatment combinations of GA_3 and Mangiferin produced a positive response for most floral and associated traits. GA_3 at 40-60 ppm or GA_3 +1.5% boric acid influenced more than one character: duration of opening of florets, stigma exertion, grain yield $plant^{-1}$, plant height, and panicle exertion. The treatment with GA_3 +1.5% boric acid was one of the most effective combinations as it influenced almost all the characters studied. Mangiferin in different combinations and concentrations also responded like GA_3 . Mangiferin alone (60 ppm) or in combination with boric acid influenced

many traits: duration of opening of florets, stigma exertion, angle of opened florets, grain yield ha^{-1} , plant height, and panicle exertion. All these traits recorded higher values than the control. The treatment containing GA_3 or Mangiferin (60 ppm) along with flag leaf clipping and rope pulling had much higher values for duration of opening of florets and stigma exertion than the control. Another important finding was the use of glycine in enhancing outcrossing in rice. GA_3 and glycine (40 ppm each) applied together resulted in 23% more yield than with the control. ■

Synchronization studies in hybrid rice seed production

S. Singh, B. C. Viraktamath, M. S. Ramesha, C. H. M. Vijayakumar, and M. I. Ahmed, Directorate of Rice Research, Rajendranagar, Hyderabad 500030, India

The two parents of a hybrid combination differ in their growth duration and therefore flower at different times even when sown on the same date. To produce hybrid seed successfully on a commercial scale, male and female parents planted side by side in a fixed row ratio should flower simultaneously, which is called synchronization. Synchronized flowering between two parental lines of different growth duration can be achieved by seeding them on different dates which is termed seeding interval (SI). The method of arriving at an SI using growth duration is simple to practice. In this method, the difference between parental lines in the number of days to initial heading or 50% flowering from seeding is used to determine SI. The growth duration of a variety, however, is known to be influenced by seasonal and weather conditions. Therefore, it is essential to determine an SI between the two parents of a hybrid for each season and location. The present study aimed at understanding the effect of different seeding dates in a season on growth duration

and its implications in hybrid seed production. The material consisted of 19 restorers belonging to different maturity groups—early (6), medium (5), and late (8)—and 3 cytoplasmic male sterile (CMS) lines with their maintainers. All were sown on five different dates from 11 Jun 1994 at 5-d intervals. The seedlings were uprooted 30 d after sowing and planted in a randomized block design with three replications at a spacing of 20×15 cm. Observations on initial heading and days to 50% flowering were recorded for each entry and in each replication. The first and last sowings increased growth duration irrespective of the material used; the last sowing on 1 Jul increased growth duration by 5-8 d in restorers, 4 d in CMS lines, and 12 d in maintainers compared with the first sowing. Other sowings did not influence growth duration markedly.

The results clearly show that there is a definite time period for sowing within which growth duration is not affected significantly. Therefore, growth duration could safely be used to determine SIs to ensure synchronized flowering in parental lines. Studies should be conducted for a given hybrid combination at each seed production location and for each season. Seeding interval determined by growth duration would then become a much more reliable parameter for long-term use. ■

Effect of seedling age on flowering time in A, B, and R lines

B. C. Viraktamath, S. Singh, C. H. M. Vijayakumar, M. S. Ramesha, and M. I. Ahmed, Directorate of Rice Research, Rajendranagar, Hyderabad 500030, India

Flowering time in parental lines plays a vital role in hybrid rice seed production. Transplanting rice seedlings at the right age assumes special significance in obtaining higher yields in cultivation as well as in hybrid seed production. In

conditions where timely planting is not possible because of unavoidable circumstances, one is bound to transplant aged seedlings. In hybrid rice seed production, in spite of staggered seeding, simultaneous planting of male and female parents is preferred to avoid inconvenience and wasted labor. An experiment was therefore conducted during the 1994 wet season to find out the effect of seedling age at transplanting on flowering time in A, B, and R lines. The experiment was laid out in a randomized block design using five cytoplasmic male sterile lines along with their corresponding maintainers, six restorer lines, and one check variety in three replications at a spacing of 20 × 15 cm. Sequential transplanting was done at an interval of 5 d using 15-50-d-old seedlings. Observations were recorded on days to 50% flowering.

The results showed that seedling age exerted a significant and positive effect on flowering; older seedlings at transplanting delayed flowering in all the lines studied. Instead of using seedlings of the optimum age (20 d), transplanting 15-d-old seedlings advanced flowering by 1 d in all the lines. When 25-d-old seedlings were used for transplanting, flowering delay was negligible in the R and B lines, but delay was 1 d in the A line. Flowering in the R lines was delayed markedly (3 d), followed by A and B lines (2 d), when 30-d-old seedlings were transplanted.

Restorer lines, which generally have a longer growth duration than their female counterparts, are sown first to produce hybrid rice seed. Therefore, at the time of transplanting, R line seedlings would be older than A line ones. Recent studies have indicated that the optimum standard of synchronization is that the female parent should flower 1 or 2 d earlier than the male parent.

Our study indicated that flowering was advanced by 1 d in A lines when 15-d-old seedlings were transplanted; it remained the same in B and R lines if 20-25-d-old seedlings were transplanted. In a hybrid combination involving a male parent with 10 d

longer growth duration than the female parent, simultaneous transplanting using 15-d-old A line seedlings and 20-25-d-old seedlings of B and R lines can be done without affecting the expected time of flowering. Transplanting seedlings aged more than 30 d showed positive and similar effects in delaying flowering in A, B, and R lines. The results in our studies indicate that similar information for the parents of commercial hybrids must be obtained in both seasons in the target area prior to large-scale seed production. ■

Storage potential of parental lines of hybrid rice

S. R. Prabakaran, Center for Biotechnology, Pondicherry University, Pondicherry 605104 and A. S. Ponnuswamy, Seed Technology Department, Tamil Nadu Agricultural University, Coimbatore, India

To elucidate the storability of parental lines of hybrid rice, we studied seed quality parameters (such as germinability and vigor index) and some biochemical traits. Seeds of different parental lines of hybrid rice—A lines (IR62829A and IR58025A), B lines (IR62829B and IR58025B), and R lines (IR10198-66-2R, AS89044, Pusa 150R, C20, and C22) having superior germinability—were stored in cloth and 400-gauge polyethylene bags. The seeds were evaluated for seed quality parameters at bimonthly intervals for 12 mo. Finally, they were subjected to accelerated aging for 9 d in an aging chamber (40 °C and 100% relative humidity).

IR10198-66-2R and AS89044 (R lines) maintained prolonged viability, whereas deterioration was faster in C20. A lines usually recorded high germinability initially but deteriorated faster than their respective maintainers during storage. A similar trend was noticed in dry matter production and vigor index. Biochemical analysis showed a steady decrease in dehydrogenase activity and an increase in both

free sugars and electrical conductivity of seed leachates as the storage period increased. Among the containers tested, the polyethylene bag proved its superiority over the cloth bag in maintaining vigor and viability, probably because of less influence from external factors such as relative humidity or temperature. It is obvious from the study that, besides container and genotype influence, the male sterility system also has a key role in seed storability. ■

Dormancy of seeds of some rice hybrids and their parents

V. Bhaskar, A. H. Krishnamurthy, R. M. Radhakrishna, and B. V. Chandra, Regional Research Station, VC Farm, Mandya 571405, Karnataka, India

The extent of seed dormancy in hybrids and their parents was investigated during the 1994 wet season. Harvested seeds from parents, hybrids, and check varieties were stored in paper bags and tested for germination at 5-d intervals. The study included the hybrids IR58025A / IR9761-19-R and IR58025A / IR29723-143-3-2-1R, male parent IR62829A, and check varieties Mandya Vijaya and IR20.

The results indicated that both cytoplasmic male sterile (CMS) lines, IR58025A and IR62829A, break dormancy 25 d after maturity and record more than 90% germination. The hybrid IR58025A / IR9761-19-1R recorded 72% germination after 25 d and 88% after 30 d. Its restorer took 30 d to break dormancy, with 84% germination. The other hybrid, IR58025A / IR29723-143-3-2-1R, recorded 92% germination after 30 d, whereas IR29723-143-3-2-1R did not germinate at all even after 30 d. It took 45 d after harvest to record more than 85% germination. Check varieties Mandya Vijaya and IR20 broke dormancy after 20 d. The results demonstrated that CMS lines IR58025A and IR62829A can be used for sowing